

D8.1

Communication and Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy

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Contributors

NAME	ORGANISATION
Valeria Mingardi	APRE
Chiara Pocaterra	APRE
Sara Silvi	APRE

Peer Reviews

NAME	ORGANISATION
Mariana Fernandez	SIE
Korinna Varga	ÖMKI

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Abbreviations

CBE JU	Circular Bio-Based Europe Joint Undertaking
CEE	Central and Eastern Europe
CET	Communication Expert Team
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DG AGRI	Directorate-General for Agriculture
DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 funding program
SMEs	Small Medium Enterprises
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MS	Member State(s)
SMEs	Small Medium Enterprises
TWG	Thematic Working Groups
WP	Work Package

Introduction to the project

BOOST4BIOEAST is a Coordination and Support Action funded by the European Commission developed to support the BIOEAST Initiative with the aim of empowering national stakeholders in the Central Eastern European and Baltic countries for the development of national bioeconomy action plans and to build long-lasting structures and spaces of dialogue for national and macro-regional cooperation. The project will enrich knowledge on the bioeconomy and stimulate related research and innovation across the macro-region.

Executive summary

Communication and dissemination are essential to maximise the impact of BOOST4BIOEAST project's goals and results. Through communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, the consortium will be able to ensure visibility and amplify stakeholders' engagement which will effectively contribute to achieve BOOST4BIOEAST objectives. The project will make use of the EU H2020 and Horizon Europe dissemination and communication best practices and follow a strategic implementation of these activities. These will be tailored to meet the needs and interests of the project's target groups.

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a reference document for strategically and effectively disseminating knowledge and information regarding BOOST4BIOEAST throughout the project's lifetime. Furthermore, this document builds upon what was described in BOOST4BIOEAST's Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement, in terms of what should be done to ensure effective communication and dissemination about the project and its outcomes.

This deliverable is also a guide for project partners on how to approach the promotion of the project and maximise its impact using the right tools and channels, and engaging stakeholders through targeted messages and channels. Finally, this strategy further indicates the roles and responsibilities of the partners related to communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

1 Introduction

BOOST4BIOEAST aims to empower national stakeholders in the Central Eastern European and Baltic countries (CEE macro-region) for the development of national bioeconomy action plans, and to build long-lasting structures and spaces of dialogue for national and macro-regional cooperation. The project was developed to support the BIOEAST Initiative¹ (<https://bioeast.eu/>) and follows the footsteps of the BIOEASTsUP H2020 project, its predecessor, building upon its outcomes of macro-regional networking among bioeconomy experts and policymakers. To further boost the active participation of all stakeholders and networks in bioeconomy policy development, project partners work towards establishing 11 national BIOEAST HUBs across the CEE macro-region. The BIOEAST HUBs will be the national platforms under which capacities are built and the different stakeholders of the bioeconomy are mobilised to effectively contribute to and take part in decision-making processes using participatory approaches.

Bioeconomy is one of the key pillars that the European Commission (EC) has identified as fundamental to achieving climate neutrality and sustainability in the Member States (EC 2018). In particular, the engagement of local stakeholders allows a deeper strengthening and upholding of processes and practices, ensuring the participation of all actors for the creation and adoption of bioeconomy policies.

This strategy for communication, dissemination and exploitation (hereafter referred to as DEC Strategy) aims at outlining an adequate and impactful approach towards awareness raising and outreach, built upon the idea that the involvement of all sectoral actors will enrich and bolster bioeconomy policies in the CEE macro-region. As first step, in Chapter 2, the definitions of communication, dissemination and exploitation will be clarified along with the difference between these terms. Then, Chapter 3 details thoroughly the BOOST4BIOEAST communication and dissemination strategy describing the vision and goals of the activity, the main target groups, tools and channels used, different roles and monitoring of activities. Chapter 4 is solely dedicated to the preliminary exploitation strategy of the project.

Work Package 8 (WP8) is responsible for project communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities with the following specific objectives:

- To maximise the project's impact and ensure its visibility through the DEC Strategy.
- To raise awareness on bioeconomy towards the target groups (BIOEAST public bodies, academia, research, civil society, bio-based entrepreneurs) across the macro-region.

¹ The Central and Eastern European Initiative for Knowledge-based Agriculture, Forestry and Aquaculture in the Bioeconomy. BIOEAST in short, provides a common research and innovation strategic framework for the development of sustainable bioeconomies for Central and Eastern European countries. The current members of the open initiative are Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland and Slovakia, Bulgaria, Croatia, Latvia, Lithuania, Estonia, Romania and Slovenia.

- To continuously support and manage the daily operation of the Knowledge Platform, in connection to the WP5 (Boosting Bioeconomy Education, Learning & BIOEAST Unit Net).
- To build and maintain connections with relevant projects and initiatives, and to create synergies in promoting bioeconomy.
- To stimulate the decision-making processes towards the bioeconomy transition in Member States.

WP8 activities concerning “impact maximisation” will leverage results and bring them to an upper level, reaching the widest possible audience of relevant stakeholders and engaging them in the project activities and the exploitation of results.

This deliverable is a living document which will be updated at M17 (*D8.2 - Communication and Dissemination and Exploitation Activities Report*) and evaluated at the end of the project (M36) as *D8.3 - Communication and Dissemination and Exploitation Activities Report - Final update*.

2 Communication, dissemination and exploitation definitions and approach

Communication, dissemination and exploitation are essential to the success and impact of BOOST4BIOEAST objectives and its expected results. At the core of the communication and dissemination tasks, there is the constant sharing of relevant information to the project’s target audience. This flow of content and materials should be strategically and effectively conducted by partners throughout the project implementation to ensure involvement and engagement of all audiences.

To correctly plan a DEC Strategy that reaches the objectives highlighted in the previous paragraphs, it is useful to point out the differences between communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, which are often confused.

What is the difference between communication, dissemination, and exploitation in the context of Horizon Europe (REA 2023)?

Communication means informing, promoting and communicating about the project, its activities and results reaching out to multiple audiences (citizens, the media, etc.). Communication therefore requires having a well-designed strategy, conveying clear messages, and using the right communication channels from the very start of the project and until its end.

Dissemination is about making the results of the project public and available to all stakeholders who can learn about and possibly be interested in using them. Such stakeholders can include, but are not limited to, public authorities, industry, policymakers, sectors of interest, civil society etc. Dissemination

can translate into the publication of project results in scientific magazines, scientific or targeted conferences and events, and databases.

Exploitation is about making use of project results for commercial, societal and/or political purposes and impacts. Exploitation of results can be performed by researchers, industry, and generally all stakeholders that can make use of them including public authorities, industrial authorities, policymakers, civil society etc. Exploitation activities need to be driven by a roadmap. They take place usually towards the end of the project and beyond but can be implemented as soon as the project has produced exploitable results.

Communication, dissemination, and exploitation are closely intertwined. Communication and dissemination can make use of the same tools and channels while addressing different audiences for different matters. Dissemination prepares the use, i.e., the future exploitation of project results as it raises awareness among key target groups, which might later become involved in the exploitation paths of certain project results.

The proposed DEC Strategy will follow a so-called 6W approach (why, who, what, where, when and how) (Ferrell and Hartline 2011) to ensure that every dissemination opportunity is adequately exploited during and by the project, clearly identifying:

- **Why to communicate and disseminate:** identify the objectives of the communication and dissemination.
- **To Whom to communicate and disseminate:** define primary and secondary target audiences.
- **What to communicate and disseminate:** different audiences have different interests and needs which need to be addressed with different key messages.
- **How to communicate and disseminate:** different audiences will be reached and addressed through different channels. To be efficient, communication and dissemination activities must be well-coordinated and monitored.
- **Where to communicate and disseminate:** the project has to communicate and disseminate to all its target audiences all over Europe.
- **When to communicate and disseminate:** the project communication and dissemination both must run throughout the project, with long-lasting and scheduled actions, and take advantage of opportunities that may arise during the project.

3 BOOST4BIOEAST Communication and Dissemination Strategy

3.1 Objectives of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy

Why should we communicate and disseminate? What are the communication and dissemination objectives of the project?

Communication and dissemination activities are an essential contribution towards the adoption of bioeconomy policies across BOOST4BIOEAST target regions, and, in general, throughout the whole European Union.

The **overall vision for communication** activities is **to develop and share content and materials that relate to project activities while highlighting the relevance and benefits of bioeconomy for the different target groups to be involved**. For **dissemination**, the objective is **promoting the activities and results of BOOST4BIOEAST WPs, so that stakeholders will be able to easily and consistently adopt and implement them**.

Specifically, communication activities will be oriented towards increasing awareness on the importance of the transition towards a widespread application of bioeconomy practices, not only in the CEE macro-region, but also all over Europe. Dissemination tools will help achieve this objective through their systematic use to distribute and promote results among the key target groups identified in Section 3.2.

Moreover, both communication and dissemination efforts have the objective of promoting the establishment and activities of the 11 national HUBs created during the first year of the project. The HUBs are fundamental points of connection to national bioeconomy stakeholders and will act as catalysts to communicate and disseminate information, content, and materials about the project as well. The national HUBs will be essential to communicate with target groups in their native languages, amplifying the project's reach, accessibility, and inclusivity.

The project's DEC Strategy also aims to build an ecosystem with similar projects, in order to create a cluster that is able to amplify and highlight these initiatives' efforts for the uptake of bioeconomy practices all over Europe. The whole consortium is committed to sharing knowledge and exchange practices to fortify and mutually promote relevant results. The networking strategy on how to initially approach this goal will be specified in sub-section 3.3.2.

Finally, communication and dissemination activities also have the objective of contributing to policymaking processes related to the uptake of bioeconomy practices. Boosting the dialogue

between policymakers, researchers and experts will be carried out through the communication and dissemination activities of the national HUBs, and through the organization of regular macro-regional bioeconomy conferences, webinars and ad-hoc national events.

3.2 Target groups, stakeholders, audience, and key messages

The communication and dissemination strategy of the project will deliver key messages to target audiences using tools and channels fitting their needs and interests. This section answers the “to Whom to communicate and disseminate” and “What to communicate and disseminate” questions.

During the preparation of BOOST4BIOEAST proposal, a list of relevant target groups to be addressed and engaged has been developed by the consortium. These groups are representatives of all sectors and value chains of the bioeconomy (from production to policy). The engagement of these groups has already proven successful during the project BIOEASTsUP (supporting project of the BIOEAST Initiative between 2019-2023), which is the starting point of BOOST4BIOEAST’s objectives and results.

To make the DEC Strategy more impactful and efficient, BOOST4BIOEAST target groups have been differentiated into external and internal stakeholders, to better tailor tasks and activities for each category. *External stakeholders* are the target groups and audiences identified as the most relevant to use and promote BOOST4BIOEAST results to throughout and beyond the project lifetime. The target groups listed in the Table 1 will be addressed with tailored messages based on their engagement in the project activities. *Internal stakeholders* are consortium members (mainly communication specialists) that are involved in communication and dissemination activities. They are included in the project’s Communication Expert Team (CET), as a reference point for the tailoring of project messages at local level. CET members are crucial to understand the communication needs and interests of external stakeholders, in order to better engage them in project activities.

In the following table, the main target groups identified for the project are listed with some examples (non-exhaustive) of organizations or associations.

Table 1. The main target groups of BOOST4BIOEAST

Level	Stakeholders	Specific target groups
External audience	Research communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research institutions of BOOST4BIOEAST. • Research institutions of other related Horizon Europe projects (e.g. CEE2ACT, BBionets, ShapingBio). • Bioeconomy-related universities, academics, students, independent researchers active in the BIOEAST macro-region. • Bioeconomy-related universities, academics, students, independent researchers active outside the BIOEAST macro-region (other EU countries).
External audience	Regional, national, and international public institutions, funders, and decision-makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Commission (DG RTD). • EuropaBio • Circular Bio-Based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU) • EU Missions (Soil, Climate change, Water) • National public administrations, funding bodies and authorities involved in bioeconomy across the BIOEAST macro-region.
External audience	Industry representatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bioeconomy start-ups and SMEs. • Farmers, foresters, processors, industries with interest in bioeconomy. • Innovation brokers and private investors with interest in bioeconomy.
External audience	General public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil society in BIOEAST macro-region and active outside the BIOEAST macro-region (other EU countries). • NGOs with interest in bioeconomy. • Consumers and consumer organisations with interest in bioeconomy in the macro-region and active outside the BIOEAST macro-region (other EU countries).

Internal audience	BOOST4BIOEAST Communication Management Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Team composed of the Coordinators (ÖMKI, SIE), WP8 leader (APRE), WP8 Task leaders (TRUST-IT, DBFZ), and partners' representatives.
	BOOST4BIOEAST CET	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Each HUB has appointed a specific communication expert (or small team) to work in WP8 activities to facilitate communication with national stakeholders.

Moreover, the HUBs will carry out this DEC strategy locally, to involve all relevant national bioeconomy actors through effective national tools and channels. Particularly, national-level bioeconomy communication and awareness-raising activities will make use of national languages, as a more direct and effective engagement approach.

The key messages highlighted during these first months of the project include:

- What is the project about and what are its expected impacts?
- What are the project objectives?
- Who is involved in the project?
- Which main activities are planned? Which results are expected?
- Who is addressed by the project/who can benefit from its activities and results, and how?

The messages listed above should be addressed through all promotional channels of the project (such as the BOOST4BIOEAST website, and social media accounts) detailed in Section 3.3.

Examples of content that will be used to create dissemination opportunities as the project develops are:

- Promotion of the BIOEAST Initiative and related events and developments.
- Presentation of BOOST4BIOEAST partners and their role in project activities.
- Public deliverables and milestones achieved: informing all target audiences of project progress and what it means in terms of use of results.
- Bioeconomy and policymaking: promoting bioeconomy policy advancements in the CEE region and beyond to demonstrate how adoption of its practices and processes benefits the different target audiences.
- Relevant events organised by BOOST4BIOEAST, the HUBs, the TWGs and other bioeconomy-related projects.

- Sustainable development through bioeconomy in the macro-region: sharing information to the general public on how bioeconomy is helping a sustainable growth and reaching European policy targets.
- Synergies with national, regional, or international institutions and EU projects: promotion of activities or results that are relevant to BOOST4BIOEAST aims and objectives to amplify the project's impact.

A specific focus will be dedicated to related EU funded projects, to amplify each other's messages and audiences. APRE, in collaboration with all project partners, is mapping all the relevant projects and initiatives in order to establish a clustering network to collaborate on the project's activities and strengthen knowledge exchange for uptake and replication potential of the project's outputs across Europe and beyond.

An initial contact and cooperation have been set with projects RuralBIOUp, BIOloc, CEE2ACT, GenB, ShapingBIO, and Engage4BIO, and with the EUBIONet initiative. Moreover, based on the analysis mapping done in T2.1, completed in M4, synergies are being explored with all the relevant existing bioeconomy networks (related to EU Missions, CBE JU, EuropaBio). The result will be the organization of an online mobilization and mutual learning workshop that will involve not only the EU projects mentioned above, but also experts' groups, networks and communities of practice active in the sectors of bioeconomy.

All the activities explained above will be performed by actively using the project's website and social media channels. In particular, the website will inform stakeholders about the BIOEAST Initiative and the BOOST4BIOEAST project in general and provide access to its main outputs and it will be the entry point for the Knowledge Platform. Social media accounts will provide a channel to reach target groups, promote the project, disseminate its results and raise awareness about relevant events and initiatives. The project will also leverage partners' social media accounts and websites, which have an already established number of local and international followers.

Table 2 below explains how the activities of the DEC Strategy relate to BOOST4BIOEAST external target groups.

Table 2. Activities, tools and channels of the DEC Strategy per target group

Stakeholder categories	Key engagement	Project website	Social media	Newsletters and press releases	Communication promotional materials	Events	Policy briefs and papers	Knowledge Platform	Peer-reviewed publications	Journal articles
Research communities	Access to funding, networking, and visibility to encourage the development and use of innovative technologies. Provide opportunities for future professionals to gain practical experience and develop skills. Boost collaboration, access funding and provide a platform to share their knowledge and expertise.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Regional, national, and international public Institutions, funders, and decision-makers	Access to funding, networking, and visibility to encourage use of innovative technologies, leading to the creation of jobs. Provide opportunities for future professionals to gain practical experience and develop skills.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Industry representatives	Access to funding, networking, and visibility to encourage innovation, leading to the creation of jobs, involvement in the decision-making process.	X	X	X	X	X		X		
General public	Boost collaboration and provide relevant information for decision-making processes. Access to state-of-the-art bioeconomy innovations.	X	X	X	X	X				

3.3 Communication and dissemination tools and channels

As presented above, different target audiences have different uses and interests and therefore must be addressed by a complementary set of tools. This section presents the tools set up for the project communication and dissemination, answering “How to communicate and disseminate” and “What to communicate and disseminate”.

Publications by BOOST4BIOEAST will aim at sharing information about goals, activities and results of the project and motivate stakeholders and target groups to engage, participate, and provide feedback in relevant activities. Most tools and channels for communication and dissemination tasks and activities have been set up during the first six months of project implementation.

This work is focused on the creation of promotional materials, that will be coherently used throughout the project as vehicles to disseminate and communicate information about the project and its achievements.

3.3.1 Communication tools and channels

Overview of the envisaged **communication** tools and channels of the project:

- *BIOEAST and BOOST4BIOEAST website* completed with all project and Initiative relevant information and results.
- *BIOEAST and BOOST4BIOEAST social media channels*: LinkedIn, X, and Facebook. These channels are used to promote project activities and events, and to engage stakeholders on the project topic.
- *Project’s visual identity* to create a coherent and appealing image.
- *Project’s Brand Manual* on how to relate to project’s visual identity.
- *Project flyer* giving an overview of the project objectives, main activities and expected results.
- *Project roll-up* to use during events, with QR code promoting the website and a summary of the project’s goals.
- *Deliverables, milestones, and presentation templates* to facilitate the sharing of project activities and results.
- *Newsletters and press releases* that inform on important project milestones and update on the progress achieved.
- *Project videos* to highlight the main project goals, activities and achievements.
- Information, knowledge exchange, and promotion with other relevant initiatives (e.g. EU funded projects) for the exploitation of synergies.
- Participation in relevant external events and conferences of interest.

BOOST4BIOEAST WEBSITE

The BOOST4BIOEAST website is hosted in the BIOEAST Initiative’s domain and webpage (which previously hosted the BIOEASTsUP project) to highlight and strengthen continuity between the Initiative and two projects and make use of existing visitors. Trust-IT has remodelled the previous version of the website basing their modifications on feedback provided during sessions organized with all the partners. The website represents the first entry point for raising awareness about the project and contains a general presentation of the project objectives and the consortium as well as all public information related to the project activities, results, events etc.

The website is accessible through the URL <https://bioeast.eu/>, and integrates the elements of the BOOST4BIOEAST visual identity. The content of the website is continuously updated as the project progresses.

Figure 1. The BIOEAST and BOOST4BIOEAST website

SOCIAL MEDIA

Social media is a useful tool to quickly reach different groups of audiences, allowing partners to create a community consisting of people likely to be interested in implementation of outputs and results. In this context, APRE will use the power of social networks to enable a more active communication and dissemination strategy towards a varied range of communities.

LINKEDIN

BOOST4BIOEAST will make use of the previous project’s LinkedIn account, changing the name from “BIOEAST & BIOEASTsUP” to “BIOEAST & BOOST4BIOEAST”.

LinkedIn is a work-related network through which the project can address very specific, professional target groups relevant for bioeconomy. It is mainly functional for targeted

networking and to create a growing network in which the status of the project, but also project outcomes, can be shared. The main aim is to reach the main target groups especially international industry, policy, and research community for BOOST4BIOEAST outputs and results. The link to the project's LinkedIn profile is: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/52193691/admin/dashboard/>

Figure 2. BOOST4BIOEAST's LinkedIn profile

X

X is an innovative and youth-oriented social platform that allows and promotes further engagement of identified target groups through its interactive nature.

The former account "BIOEAST & BIOEASTsUP" has been renamed to "BIOEAST & BOOST4BIOEAST", as it has for LinkedIn. Using already existing accounts allows us to start with a solid follower base, that is already interested and engaged with the topics treated. On X, due to limited characters, the posts shared will be more direct and targeted towards policymakers, authorities of various levels, and similar projects and initiatives. The project's X profile is active at this link: <https://x.com/bioeastsup>.

BIOEAST & BOOST4BIOEAST

@bioeastsup

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement 101133398.

📍 Hungary 🔗 bioeastsup.eu 📅 Joined November 2019

263 Following 443 Followers

Figure 3. BOOST4BIOEAST's X profile

FACEBOOK

A new page on Facebook has been created to stimulate an exchange of ideas and visions among all stakeholder groups. Facebook is a popular platform that tends to develop a sense of community and engage in discussions through open comments.

In this account, topics and ideas will be shared with the audience to obtain feedback and insights on the project results and outputs. The project's Facebook page is to be found at this link: <https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61558213562532>.

Figure 4. BOOST4BIOEAST's Facebook profile

PROMOTIONAL COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

VISUAL IDENTITY

Another fundamental support to ensure an effective implementation of the DEC strategy is the project's **visual identity**, also called **brand identity**. It was developed during the first months of the project, starting from the creation of the BOOST4BIOEAST logo.

Figure 5. BOOST4BIOEAST logo

The logo was created taking into account the BIOEAST Initiative logo, using colours on the same palette, as a way to connect and highlight the continuation between the Initiative and the project. Moreover, the logo encompasses symbols that shows connection to bioeconomy and growth. The use of the logo, its application, and its variations (monochrome, favicon, and vertical versions) have been gathered in the Brand Manual.

BRAND MANUAL

APRE developed the Brand Manual based on the project's logo to support partners in navigating the BOOST4BIOEAST's visual identity. The document contains the analysis of the elements composing the project's logo and further elaborates on its creation process and its meaning.

The Brand Manual has been uploaded to the project's common repository space (SharePoint), allowing each project partner to have easy access for consultation. Moreover, APRE Team is always reachable and available to clarify the use of visual identity or to develop ad-hoc materials for partner's specific needs.

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visual identity color palette

COLOR	PRIMARY MEANING	SECONDARY MEANING
#106a39	nature east	welfare knowledge
#febb25	positivity energy	hope originality
#eae4c0	earth resilience	simplicity trust

The color palette was chosen to resume those of previous projects, revising it only in shades and saturation. The aim is to give a feeling of continuity with the past while having the freedom to deviate from previous symbols.

A neutral color is added to be used in the bases and neutral elements.

logo concept

This logo idea starts by interpreting the concept of "boost" as "something" to grow (branch) and is represented by a plant. Obviously this symbolism also refers to the **bioeconomy**, the main topic of the project.

+
+
PROPOSAL LOGO
=

Figures 6-11. Excerpts from BOOST4BIOEAST's Brand Manual

FLYER

A BOOST4BIOEAST flyer has been developed and will be used to present the project, its goals and the consortium. The project flyer reflects the ideas and planned activities of the project as a first step and might be updated with information about major outcomes and results as a second step, if deemed useful.

It serves as a visually attractive presentation to influential stakeholders – experts, societal actors, media representatives, etc. The first version of the flyer explains the background and goals of the project, indicates the targeted results, and provides information on national HUBs and relevant contacts.

The flyer will be available in digital (pdf) and printable versions as well.

Figure 12-13. The project flyer (front and back)

ROLL-UP

To use during events, the roll-up is an effective way to communicate the project's key points and make an impression on the public. The roll-up gives a glimpse at the project's aims and informs about major communication channels such as the website URL and social media accounts to allow anyone to get in touch with the project easily.

The banners have been produced in digital versions for the social media accounts, together with the logos that fit the various platforms' specific requirements.

Figure 14. BOOST4BIOEAST roll-up

DELIVERABLES, MILESTONES AND PRESENTATION TEMPLATES

Finally, APRE has developed three templates to be used to formalize and share project results: two in Word format for project's deliverables and milestones, and one in PowerPoint format to present various types of content related to project's tasks and activities.

The templates are available for download on the project's SharePoint and contain guidelines for facilitating their use.

Figure 15-17. First pages of the project's deliverable, milestone and presentation templates

NEWSLETTERS AND PRESS RELEASES

To disseminate project results and keep stakeholders informed about relevant aspects of the project and its activities, newsletters and press releases will be periodically shared in the project mailing list, on the project's website, and other EU-appointed tools (e.g. Cordis).

Figure 18. The project's 1st press release published on the project's website

VIDEOS

As our contemporary communication is built on images, and specifically on videos, APRE will create three videos to highlight the project's most relevant aspects. These videos will be used for general promotion and will reflect BOOST4BIOEAST progress throughout the implementation of the activities.

SYNERGIES WITH OTHER PROJECTS AND ORGANIZATIONS

To maximise both regional and EU-wide visibility and enhance long-term synergies, BOOST4BIOEAST partners, led by APRE, will actively work on establishing relationships with strategic EU actors and other funded projects. APRE will map all the relevant projects and initiatives (for potential clustering) and will contact all the stakeholders to establish a collaboration on the project's activities. Where possible, synergies will also be created with organisations that have endorsed the project.

The overall aim of the networking and exchange around synergies will be to raise awareness within relevant target groups, to engage relevant actors in project activities, and to serve common goals, broadening as such the impact of BOOST4BIOEAST and the initiatives it will be collaborating with.

PARTICIPATION AT RELEVANT EVENTS

All project partners are committed to participating at relevant sectoral events (from local, national to international levels) to promote the project's goals, activities, and results. Taking part in bioeconomy-related events will allow for networking and spreading information about

BOOST4BIOEAST results to a varied group of stakeholders and raising interest and awareness about the project.

3.3.2 Dissemination tools and channels

In terms of **dissemination** activities, the project will make use of the following tools and channels:

- *Policy briefs and policy recommendations* to promote and disseminate relevant findings to identified target groups.
- *BOOST4BIOEAST webinars* to ensure efficient knowledge transfer to interested audiences.
- The *Knowledge Platform*, connected to the project's website, will be the repository space for bioeconomy-related information, educational materials and knowledge.
- If possible, *scientific publications and peer-reviewed articles* will inform stakeholders on research relevant outputs of the project (mainly connected to the results of the multi-dimensional mapping and analysis in WP3-WP4-WP5).
- Project partners will also present their results at different *conferences and public events*.

POLICY BRIEFS AND POLICY RECCOMENDATIONS

Throughout project implementation, a series of briefs and recommendations targeted towards policymakers of various levels (regional, national, and international) will be produced by the consortium.

In particular, at M35 DBFZ will provide a policy brief that will include all the priorities emerged during the implementation of BOOST4BIOEAST activities, with the goal of stimulating the transition towards the bioeconomy in macro-regional policymaking processes.

WEBINARS AND WORKSHOPS

A series of webinars (one/year) will be organized on various topics identified by the HUBs and TWGs and to share insights from the project. With the aim of transferring knowledge, the webinars will be open to all stakeholders and consider different benefits to appeal to all target groups. DBFZ will provide a structure in the form of recommendations to organize two online workshops aimed at policymakers and sectoral experts.

Moreover, one online mobilization and mutual learning workshop will be organized involving identified EU projects, experts' groups, networks and communities of practice in various relevant domains.

KNOWLEDGE PLATFORM

The BIOEAST Knowledge Platform, launched in M6, is a repository of knowledge materials and relevant information on bioeconomy, allowing stakeholders to easily access and share information and content on the topic. The Platform will be a precious dissemination tool, as it will be an engaging instrument for all macro-regional stakeholders available in 11 languages (countries of the macro-region) and English.

By guaranteeing easy access and a constant updating of its content, the Knowledge Platform will also represent a focal point to store and distribute project results to its final users.

SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS AND PEER-REVIEWED ARTICLES

The BOOST4BIOEAST consortium is planning to publish two peer-reviewed articles on research relevant outputs by the end of the project. The project is not a Research and Innovation Action (RIA), therefore conducting research is not the objective, still through the multidimensional mapping exercise (WP3-WP4-WP5), relevant results will be generated which can serve as a basis for scientific publications. The articles are to be published in Open Access (OA) in scientific journals relevant to the research outputs they will be discussing.

The knowledge, outputs, tools, and instruments gathered from this deployment will be free and available as necessary and will be deposited in a trusted repository (Green OA), under the Creative Attribution International Public License (CC BY). In parallel, the consortium will be encouraged to publish in the Open Research Europe (ORE) platform. This publication process will ensure wide dissemination of results and will contribute to the implementation of the outputs by the relevant key users.

CONFERENCES AND EVENTS

BOOST4BIOEAST's dissemination strategy foresees activities aimed at implementing knowledge management, exploitation, knowledge transfer and outreach actions. The table below is a non-exhaustive list of the events and conferences relevant for dissemination purposes.

Table 3. Events relevant for BOOST4BIOEAST dissemination purposes

Event // Purpose	T/Date	Organizer	Mode	Audience / KPI
Project Kick-off meeting // Clarifying roles and responsibilities, establish communication protocols, discussing risks and challenges	T1.4 // M1	ÖMKI	In-person	All the consortium // >30att
Annual meeting (2) // Review the progress, address outcomes, discussing future plans.	T1.4 // M12, M24	ÖMKI, ICEADR, EIHP	In-person	All the consortium // >30att
HUB kick-off meetings (national) // Establish relationships between HUB participants to ensure understanding of benefits, expectations, future acts.	T2.2 // M3-12	HUB Coordinators	In-person	HUB partners // >10 att per HUB

HUB follow-up meetings // Monitoring progress, identifying solutions, reporting achievements.	T2.2 // M10-M36	HUB Coordinators	1 in-person and 2-3 online/year	HUB partners // >10 att per HUB
Annual Bioeconomy Conference (1 per year) // HUBs and TWGs meet, network, exchange experiences, challenges and lessons learnt and explore cross-HUB collaboration opportunities to invigorate the region's bioeconomy.	T.2.2 // M12, M24, M30	ICEADR BME, EIHP	In-person	HUB & TWG reps, BIOEAST Board > 70-100 att
Inter-ministerial group meetings // Act as platforms for the identification of barriers and enablers to involve policymakers in bioeconomy and to validate policy documents produced by the project.	T2.3 // M6-M35	HUB Coordinators	1 in-person/year	National policy makers // > 10 att/ HUB
Capacity building trainings for TWGs and HUBs coordinators // Knowledge transfer and upskilling to acquire and boost necessary skills and competencies to run and animate national HUBs and TWG networks in the starting phase and in the long run.	T2.2 // M15-M28	CC	1 In-person, online courses	All HUB and TWG Coordinator // > 14 att
National meetings for science-policy development (once a year/HUB) // Discuss national bioeconomy topics and priorities and their policy implications.	T2.3 // M10-M30	HUB Coordinators	Online or in-person	All stakeholders // > 20 att per HUB
National workshop on policy needs for the use of biomass and competencies (1 per HUB) // Discussion on needs and expectations of national policymakers about the use of the multidimensional analysis in terms of the policy recommendations	T3.4 // M18-m30	HUB Coordinators	Online	HUB partners and policy makers // >10 att per HUB
BIOEAST Pitching Events // Bringing together public and private investors and winners of the OIC.	T4.3 // M24	CR HUB, EMU, CC, AA, AKI, IBF	In-person	OIC winners and investors // >12 att per HUB
OIC Design Workshop // Start of the challenge design process by defining challenge categories around the national priority areas.	T4.2 / M10	EFI	Online	HUB, TWG Coordinators and WP4 partners // > 25 att
Open Innovation Challenge Consensus Workshop // Validation of Challenges through the most appropriate categories.	T4.2 // M18	EFI	Online	Project Partners and bioeconomy stakeholders // >50 att
BIOEAST Knowledge Platform training // explain the HUB leaders how to access the platform and their mini sites and how to update the content.	T5.3 // M8	TRUST-IT	Online	HUBs coordinators // >12 att
TWG meetings (1 per year) // Progressing with TWG activities in line with the ToR, monitoring activities and ensuring thematic SRIA update.	T6.2 // M1-M36	ÖMKi, TTK, CR HUB, MARD PL, NLCSK, EIHP	Online	TWG representatives // >15-20 att per TWG

3 Validation webinars // SRIAs will then be validated through three online regional webinars where the feedback of stakeholder groups will be considered.	T6.2 // M27-M30	TTK	Online	TWG representatives and all stakeholders // >50-70 att
Science-policy dialogue workshop (macro-regional) // Focus on current sectoral research and innovation topics identified in thematic SRIAs.	T6.3 // M5-M36	AKI + ÖMKI, TTK, CR HUB, MARD PL, NLCSK, EIHP	Online	TWG representatives and policy makers // 70-100 att
Action Plan Workshops (3 per HUB) to develop or refine 11 national bioeconomy Action Plans using Three Horizons Framework (2023 Diagnose; 2030 Envision; 2023-2030 Strategize).	T7.2 // M13-M21	HUB Coordinators	Online	HUB partners // >15-20 att per HUB
Cross-fertilization workshop // enable TWG and HUB Coordinators exchange knowledge and ideas.	T7.4 // M24	4CF	In-person	TWGs and HUBs coordinators // >14 att
Prototyping training workshop for HUBs and TWGs coordinators to pilot-test the Action Plan development methodology with all National HUBs representatives.	T7.2 // M11-M12	4CF	Online	TWGs and HUBs coordinators // >14 att
Future-proofing workshops (1 per HUB) // stress-test Action Plans in changing external conditions and increase their implementation potential by addressing potential risks and opportunities.	T7.5 // M25-M30	HUB Coordinators	Online	HUB Partners // >15-20 att per HUB
European policy dialogues // continuously contribute to and monitor bioeconomy-related policymaking.	T8.4 // M12-24	DBFZ	1 in-person and 1 online	Partners and stakeholders, external policymakers // 50-70 att
Final Conference // Bringing the project to a close and ensuring that all project outcomes and deliverables are properly documented, and impact communicated.	T8.1 // M35	ÖMKI, APRE	In-person	All the consortium, external policymakers // >70-100 att

NETWORKING STRATEGY

In order to achieve a satisfactory dissemination of results, BOOST4BIOEAST is committed to reaching out and involving several EU funded projects and initiatives working on similar or related topics. The Networking Strategy below is an initial outline that will guide future activities for this task. A summary of steps taken, and a more detailed outline of networking efforts will be shared in the DEC update to be submitted at M17.

The Networking Strategy to collaborate and cooperate with these projects and initiatives is based on mutual promotion and on the establishment of synergies to amplify each other's voices. A network of related projects will evolve into a cluster actively looking for occasion to join forces in mutual events, webinars, and workshops.

APRE, as task leader, will conduct a thorough mapping of existing projects, networks and initiatives, and identify potential collaborative actions and opportunities. Then, APRE will reach out to the representatives of these projects and initiatives to set up a bilateral dialogue and understand which activities can be carried out together in terms of scope and timing. Organizing and implementing joint activities and events will allow to reach new stakeholders while avoiding the over exploitation of their time and efforts (stakeholders fatigue). A more detailed strategy with strategically relevant bioeconomy projects/initiatives, exact steps on how to be engaged with them will be elaborated in D8.2

3.4 Acknowledgement of funding and disclaimer

As indicated in the GA (article 17.2), communication and dissemination activities of the beneficiaries related to the action, dissemination activities, and any other major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and the funding statement. The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands, or text. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

The following statement will be present in all materials developed by the project: *“BOOST4BIOEAST is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”*

3.5 Planning of communication and dissemination activities

To ensure the DEC strategy stays up to date, an internal planning, coordination and monitoring process will be followed. In addition, all partners must report on their activities and opportunities through the monitoring file provided by APRE and available in the project SharePoint.

APRE, as WP8 leader, will regularly check the progress and, if needed, adjust the planning of dissemination activities. APRE will also supervise all activities and provide strategic direction when needed. APRE will further coordinate the collection of updates and news content from partners to produce news on the project’s social media accounts and website.

A *Communication and Dissemination (C&D) planning and monitoring* excel file has been shared by APRE with the partners to **plan, coordinate and report** on all communication and dissemination activities, as well as on the preparation and publishing of news and social media

posts. This excel file will be reviewed regularly and updated by APRE with the support of consortium partners. Partners will cooperate with the redaction of this file by sending news and requests by email when necessary. The consortium can also review and give feedback on the *social media editorial plan*, a document where APRE plans, collects and monitors the content to be shared on the project's social media accounts. Both files are living documents, accessible on the WP8 folder of the project's SharePoint.

Finally, WP8 activities will be discussed during the General Assembly meetings, and, if needed, during dedicated WP8 videocalls to provide a platform to review relevant issues or ideas.

3.6 The role of partners in communication and dissemination

To achieve the communication and dissemination objectives described above, concrete processes and procedures should be put in place for coordinating and implementing the dissemination strategy including communication. This section answers to the “how to communicate and disseminate” question.

To ensure and cross-check the performance of the communication and dissemination activities against the strategic goals, it is necessary to nominate the responsible partners, to follow up the implementation of activities and control the process. More specifically, dissemination of the project and dissemination of knowledge gained during the project lifetime is expected to take place through the consortium partners, their networks, and the relevant BOOST4BIOEAST's initiatives.

To optimize the communication and dissemination of project activities, the following activities will be organized:

- Continuous update of the C&D monitoring excel file and the editorial plan.
- Each partner can propose news or promote activities and events by sending them to APRE and to the Coordinators who will find the best way to share the content.
- Communication materials such as press releases or other promotional content will be published and disseminated by all partners using their respective media channels and all BOOST4BIOEAST's communication channels.

The roles for communication and dissemination activities are the following:

- WP8 is led by APRE, therefore responsible for all project related DEC activities and specifically operates the project's social media channels and implements the networking strategy.
- TRUST-IT (T5.3 and T8.2 lead) leads the development and maintenance of BIOEAST & BOOST4BIOEAST website and the Knowledge Platform.

- All partners will work closely with APRE to provide input to all C&D activities, therefore playing an important role in spreading information.

The work tasks and responsibilities are distributed as follows:

APRE – WP8 leader:

Leads the management and coordination of the WP including:

- setting up of the DEC Strategy,
- monitoring and coordinating the dissemination and communication activities throughout Europe,
- interacting with all partners for the dissemination and communication activities,
- stimulating partners to provide dissemination input, such as news for publication on the project website, etc.
- providing text of relevant news and publications related to general project activities,
- ensuring quality control of the information provided,
- creating and ensuring the adequate usage of the visual identity and templates (logo, Word and PowerPoint),
- producing promotional materials based on the contributions from partners,
- preparing and organizing the distribution of the press releases (disseminated by all partners through their channels),
- ensuring the quality of the dissemination to experts.

3.7 Communication and dissemination monitoring

Measurable targets and performance indicators are set for the communication and dissemination activities through key performance indicators (KPIs) included in the GA. The table below summarizes BOOST4BIOEAST’s KPIs regarding communication and dissemination activities.

Table 4. KPIs of the project for dissemination and communication and related activities

#	KPI	Target	Achieved at M6	Audience
1	Project website and Platform	10.000 visits	ongoing	All target groups
2	Newsletters, press releases and news	one/every 3 months	1 press release published	Research communities, public institutions and decision makers,

#	KPI	Target	Achieved at M6	Audience
				industry representatives
3	Brochure, poster, roll up, infographics	Distribution for each instrument: <150 poor, 150-300 average; >300 good	Materials developed for partners at M5	All target groups
6	Videos	3 videos (M9, M17, M24)	Not started yet	All target groups
7	Social networks	2.000 followers across 3 social media account (LinkedIn, X, Facebook)	1.170 followers reached by M6	All target groups
8	Policy briefs/papers	At least 9 policy briefs	Not started yet, by M36	Research communities, public institutions and decision makers, industry representatives
9	Issued journal papers	At least 2 issued peer reviewed papers	Not started yet, by M36	Research communities
10	Webinars	At least 3 webinars, one/year	Not started yet	Research communities, public institutions and decision makers, industry representatives

An update on the dissemination activities will be made during the consortium General Assembly meetings and all dissemination activities will be kept in the dedicated monitoring file for reporting purposes.

4 BOOST4BIOEAST exploitation strategy

4.1 Objectives

A defined plan for the exploitation of results is fundamental to ensure that consortium efforts towards the achievement of BOOST4BIOEAST's objectives will continue after the funding period using the various WP results by stakeholders and target groups.

In this preliminary exploitation plan, APRE sets up a strategy to be shared with partners to make sure that relevant Key Exploitable Results (KERs) will be identified for future applications. KERs are results from different WPs that are deemed ideal to be carried out after the end of the project (particularly relevant to stakeholders), so it is important to ensure their continued use and application.

BOOST4BIOEAST is committed to guarantee that know-how, data, and assets developed in the project will be **accessible** and **easy to be replicated** by its stakeholders. Identifying and fostering KERs will be therefore the goal of partners throughout the project lifetime, and the objective of all exploitation efforts.

BOOST4BIOEAST's exploitation activities aim to ensure that project outputs will contribute to the development of national bioeconomy action plans also after the project funding period ends. Moreover, the goals are to guarantee that project results will strengthen the BIOEAST stakeholders' knowledge and cooperation on bioeconomy issues, and bridge the existing political, financial, and educational gaps among Western and CEE countries.

The first list of exploitable assets is indicated in Section 4.3, Table 4. In *D8.3 - Communication and Dissemination and Exploitation Activities Report - Final Update* (M36), APRE will analyse new results emerged during implementation to be exploited after the project lifecycle. The deliverable will be focused on the necessary sustainability measures to be put in place to guarantee the replication of BOOST4BIOEAST products after the end of the funding period.

4.2 BOOST4BIOEAST stakeholders as key end-users for exploitation efforts

This strategy identified seven key end-user groups for exploitation of project results that are described in detail in the sub-sections below.

4.2.1 BOOST4BIOEAST partners and the BIOEAST Board

BOOST4BIOEAST partners are closely connected to the BIOEAST Board (governing body of the BIOEAST Initiative), though there are some overlaps, but the actors are not the same. The Board

is only comprised of representatives of public administrations from the BIOEAST countries, while the BOOST4BIOEAST consortium covers research organisations, universities, SMEs, non-profit and international organisation and ministries (five). This connection will ensure dissemination and cooperation for the use of project's results, that will contribute to maximising operability and presence of the BIOEAST Initiative in the CEE macro-region and beyond. Specifically, the project partners and BIOEAST Board will find benefits in the establishment of HUBs, the development of action plans, the update of thematic SRIAs and the connection with TWGs for different topics.

The Board will also be involved in building a strong connection with stakeholders, that will be carried out beyond the project's end.

4.2.2 Research communities

Scientists and researchers, and other profiles connected to the academic and scientific community are interested in the results and impact of the BOOST4BIOEAST project. They have multiple interests in bioeconomy-related outputs and results connected to the project, both in terms of further research, macro-regional network building and as support for policymaking. Stakeholders from this sector can use results for networking purposes, inspiration, information, new research ideas, new development possibilities, knowledge transfer, potential innovation as well as dissemination, reputation building, specialisation in new bioeconomy fields, visibility and teaching materials.

To ensure their involvement as final users, they will be engaged primarily through the activities of the national HUBs, the macro-regional TWGs, the Open Innovation Challenge (OIC) and also through the multidimensional mapping, policy briefs, recommendations, the journal articles, and the organization of specific webinars and events. Finally, through the Knowledge Platform, researchers and experts will be able to access materials and content relevant for their activities, ensuring their continued use and application.

4.2.3 Regional, national, and international public institutions, funders, and decision-makers

The representatives of public institutions, funders, and policymakers are at the core of the utilization and replication of project results. These actors have the power to apply, strengthen and institutionalize processes and practices through policy at different levels (regional, national, and international), that can boost bioeconomy applications not only in the BIOEAST macro-region, but also adapt in other contexts, making sure that the project's outputs and results are implemented and spread across a wide network.

Decision-makers and funders will be engaged through the activities of national HUBs, inter-ministerial groups, the macro-regional TWGs and also through policy briefs, recommendations, webinars, and the Knowledge Platforms. All these dissemination tools will allow them to gather

information and best practices on the benefits of bioeconomy in terms of sustainability and growth.

4.2.4 Industry representatives

Industrial entrepreneurs, start-ups and sectoral businesses will be included in the form of innovation opportunities, networking, and participation at the OIC and other events. Particularly through the HUBs and their activities, these key users will be provided with information to be more competitive, sustainable, integrated into policymaking, and on the implementation of bioeconomy processes.

4.2.5 Other initiatives and projects based on thematic and methodological interest

Advisors, consultants and mentors as well as social and technological innovators are key end-users. They provide different point of views and a complementary vision related to the promotion, research, co-creation, validation, activation, dynamization and evaluation of pathways and future scenarios for bioeconomy processes. They allow the improvement and strengthening of bioeconomy policies to promote sustainable development, sustainable growth, and climate neutrality in Europe, together with a change of policymakers' perceptions of the legislative processes.

This category of stakeholders will be engaged through various events from the annual BIOEAST Bioeconomy Conferences, networking events to webinars that will allow a direct presentation of results enabling an explanation of their use and of the benefits that can be achieved from their implementation.

4.2.6 General public

Professional associations, interest groups, media, foundations, NGOs, education institutions, and cultural entities (with different ages, genders and backgrounds), among others, may be interested in the BOOST4BIOEAST impact, specifically when it comes to participating in the policymaking processes.

These stakeholders, in addition to exploring the existing and future scenarios for bioeconomy applications, may also be of interest to gather feedback and perceptions for new policies both at regional and European level. In particular, these key end-users could be involved to provide feedback on perception issues, such as transparency, open access to data, carbon-free approach, new social inequalities, etc. These matters have an impact on the media, on internet platforms and on the cultural industries in general.

The key end-users coming from the public will be reached through the promotion of the Knowledge Platform that will give them access to relevant and updated content and materials on bioeconomy. While the general public will also be involved in events and webinars, the main

promotion of results and their use will come from communication tools such as social media, project website, and other printed materials.

4.3 Carrying out the exploitation strategy

The planning of exploitation will ensure the following five steps:

1. Explanation of the exploitation and Intellectual Property (IP) management methodologies and related risks.
2. Elaboration of the KERs laid down in the GA and possibly identification of new ones with the help of the partners.
3. Establishment of links and synergies with running projects and international initiatives.
4. Exploitation of project results beyond the end of the project, ensuring they are findable and accessible in the long term.

To optimize BOOST4BIOEAST’s results, exploitation activities will be analysed, discussed and defined during WP8 activities taking into account the interests and expectations of the stakeholders involved, as well as adaptation strategies to ensure that the exploitation plans stay relevant and updated during the project’s implementation phase.

The consortium has already identified a list of potential exploitable assets which are listed in Table 5. This list will be updated with information on who is planning to exploit them, who are the contributors, the market advantage, the IP background, the IP owner and with new assets if relevant. The results will be analysed by APRE in *D8.3 - Communication and Dissemination and Exploitation Activities Report – Final Update* at M36.

Table 5. List of initial exploitable assets by the project identified as per GA.

Asset/Result			Exploitation value	Key end users
National	bioeconomy	action plans	The plans provide new, complex, cross-cutting policies and incentives at national levels to move toward sustainable bioeconomy and to strengthen the capacity and competitiveness of stakeholders. Potential is to be used by the national stakeholders to develop new bioeconomy solutions or facilitate those already developed and accelerate the process of knowledge sharing, involvement in policy making for	BIOEAST Board, research community, decision and policymakers, industry representatives, general public.

	bioeconomy in the BIOEAST countries.	
Updated thematic SRIAs and BIOEAST-level SRIA	Using the updated SRIAs help BIOEAST countries to understand macro-regional research needs and priorities. Moreover, regions facing similar challenges and research priorities can be identified, further contributing to a participatory governance, fostering cross-border cooperation, and informing national and European (Horizon Europe) program development.	BIOEAST Board, research community, decision and policy makers, industry representatives.
BIOEAST Knowledge Platform	Its key aspect is the capacity to collect bioeconomy knowledge and research materials in a unique online space. The knowledge materials and information are categorized per BIOEAST country, and are accessible from decision making to everyone, without regional/national barriers.	BIOEAST Board, research community, decision and policy makers, industry representatives, other similar initiatives, general public.
Biomass and competency-related, education needs & gaps, innovation capacity, and SRIA topic-based policy recommendations	The policy recommendations produced have the ambition to disseminate evidence-based policy needs and expectations towards national policymakers in order to stimulate change in national measures.	BIOEAST Board, research community, decision and policy makers, industry representatives.

5 Conclusion

This deliverable provides a framework based on the 6W methodology to all consortium partners, outlining the core strategy to communicate, promote and highlight BOOST4BIOEAST project activities and maximising their impacts using the adequate C&D tools and channels. As project implementation moves forward, this strategy will be adapted to better respond to communication and dissemination needs, obstacles, and opportunities.

APRE will oversee and adapt the DEC Strategy, with the cooperation of all project partners, keeping in mind the specific and overall goals of the project and WP8. This deliverable should be seen as a guide that illustrates the steps that have been taken so far and plans for the coming months, until the end of the project.

This strategy is a living document which will be updated twice, at M17 (D8.2) and at M36 (D8.3), holding it accountable for reaching the foreseen KPIs and for maintaining all communication channels relevant, updated, and active.

6 References

BIOEAST Initiative website: <https://bioeast.eu/>

BOOST4BIOEAST project website: <https://bioeast.eu/objectives/>

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www.bioeast.eu

korinna.varga@biokutatas.hu

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